

1 **Energy in cancer.**

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8 Background: Cancer cells promote their survival by producing large quantities of growth factors and
9 expressing high levels of receptors for these factors. Growth factor inhibition is a therapeutic strategy in
10 medical oncology.

11 Hypothesis: Growth factor inhibition will intrinsically be accompanied by compensatory changes in
12 pathways that provide cellular energy: specifically PI3K, AKT, mTOR, and the ribosome.

13 Aim: Identify genes important for nutrient sensing and homeostatic regulation of cellular energy (e.g.,
14 amino acids and phospholipids) by measuring and studying total transcription in human cells responding
15 to and withdrawing from nutrient signals, experimentally manipulated using serum starvation, and
16 chemical and genetic kinase inhibition.

17 Datasets utilized

- 18 1. Nutrient sensing during transformation
 - 19 2. Nutrient sensing in response to growth factor signals or serum starvation
 - 20 3. Kinase inhibition (genetic)
 - 21 4. Kinase inhibition (small molecule)
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